

Potato peels-based electrodes for recording ECG and EMG signals

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ABSTRACT

Reliable measurement and acquisition of physiological parameters is among critical tasks in human health monitoring. While the presence of personalized measurement of Electrocardiography (ECG) and Electromyography (EMG) devices enables more frequent data collection, and consequently better health monitoring, it also leads to higher consumption of electrodes. On the other hand, commonly used Ag/AgCl electrodes are not free of charge or biodegradable. Therefore, their extensive use leads to higher costs and higher waste production. In this paper, we present an approach for the development of ECG/EMG electrodes that are based on biodegradable materials (two potato types). We performed successful integration of potato peel-based electrodes with the commercial device as well as with our in-house developed portable system. Measurements on 8 healthy volunteers revealed very small differences when heart rate, inter-beat-interval or normal-to-normal intervals are extracted from the ECG signal with potato peel-based and commercial Ag/AgCl electrodes. Our study demonstrates the feasibility of utilizing biodegradable potato peel-based electrodes for ECG and EMG measurements, showcasing their comparable performance to traditional Ag/AgCl electrodes in capturing physiological parameters. We introduced biodegradable electrodes as a viable and eco-friendly alternative for accurate ECG and EMG measurements, addressing the issues of electrode waste and cost associated with conventional electrodes.

1. Introduction

Electrocardiography (ECG) and surface Electromyography (EMG) are among the most often used diagnostic techniques for discovering pathological conditions even before structural changes in the heart or muscles can be observed by other methods [1]. The non-invasiveness of these methods, low costs and compact size of these medical devices have contributed to the wider spread of these methods not only in clinical practice, but also measuring at home, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdowns in many countries. Regardless of clinical or personal recording of ECG or EMG signals, the indispensable part of the data acquisition are electrodes which are the first contact between the human skin and electronic readout device. The metal surface of electrodes can be in a direct contact with the skin (in the case of dry electrodes) or through conductive gel (wet electrodes) [2].

There are various types of surface electrodes which are used for recording the ECG and EMG signals. The usual type is gelled Ag/AgCl electrodes that can be disposable or reusable. However, they require a solid hydrogel or a liquid gel to operate properly. Applying the electrolyte for a long time (for example Holter recordings) can cause some skin problems and allergic reactions [3]. If the chest suction metallic ball

electrodes are applied, some irritations or acute skin lesions on the chest can appear, after ECG examination. Because of that researchers have tried to examine alternative solutions for ECG electrodes and some of them were: (a) silver textile electrodes [4], (b) electrodes composed of nylon with rGO coating [5], (c) CNT/Ag-PDMS electrodes [6], (d) inkjet-printed textile electrodes in PEDOT:PSS [7], etc. However, both the typical Ag/AgCl disposable gelled electrodes and textile-based electrodes represent serious challenge for our environment, bearing in mind that their recycling is not straightforward and wide-spread process. Because of that, researchers studied some alternatives ways to create the electrodes for recording signals from our body. For example, authors in [8] reported using parylene C-based tattoo electrodes for ECG signal recording. L. A. Garcia-Garcia et al. studied epidermal electrodes based on coconut-oil and carbon black for the monitoring ECG signals [9]. Related to the surface electromyogram the following electrodes were reported: (a) arc-shaped silver wires electrodes in order to follow muscle fiber direction [10], (b) silver-nano wire [11], (c) carbon-based adhesive electrodes [12], textile-based electrodes [13]. The optimization of the shape and materials used for manufacturing electrodes is important to minimize the noise sources [14].

In the context of eco-friendly green agendas in many countries,

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Fig. 1. (a) Potato peel and copper foil for electrodes creation, (b) Comparison of a commercial single-use electrode and in-house developed potato-peel based, (c) Placement of electrodes for measurement of ECG and EMG signal.

turning waste to value become crucial concept. Potato peel is a common waste in our kitchen. However, potato peel has been used for removal of toxic substances [15], for edible films [16], but also in medicine, for example for dressing the burns. R. M. Dattatreya et al. reported that dressings made of boiled potato peels can be successfully used for wound healing and prevention of dehydration [17]. Potato peel does not irritate the skin as well as the potato peel extract possesses antibacterial and antioxidant properties [18].

Instead of developing gel-based or gel-free “dry” electrodes, the main idea of this paper is to utilize biocompatibility properties of potato peel, and to use its wet properties from the internal side to provide a very good contact with our skin. Joining a copper foil, we created innovative natural electrodes for measuring ECG, EMG signals as well as skin conductivity. Usage of potato peels is a key enabler of the application of these electrodes to be personalized and to be used at home, contributing to the point of care concept. We compared ECG and EMG signals recorded, on 8 volunteers, using the conventional Ag/AgCl and the proposed innovative potato peel-based electrodes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

For creation of electrodes, the potato, a tuber of the plant *Solanum tuberosum*, was bought in the local store. A potato tuber was peeled off evenly as can be seen in Fig. 1(a). A short cut was created partially separating the outer side of the peeled potato skin with the inner wet, conductive side. This was done to provide a pocket (Fig. 1(b)) for a thin copper conductive tape that should be a bridge between the conventional connection to the measurement system and the potato peel. For comparison, Fig. 1(b) shows commercial Ag/AgCl electrodes (commonly used for surface ECG and EMG data acquisition) and in-house developed new potato peel-based electrodes, which were made to be the size of the electrode, for visual purposes. Different sizes of potato peel-based electrodes were used for measurement purposes, as they adhered more firmly to the skin, by having a rectangular shape. The typical peel thickness, width and length were 1 mm, 40 mm and 15 mm, respectively.

2.2. Instruments and experimental set-up

Experimental set-up for recording ECG and EMG signals is presented in Fig. 1(c). The measured data was collected on a laptop connected with the Biopac acquisition unit (Biopac Systems Inc., Goleta, CA, USA). Eight healthy volunteers (age: 33 ± 9 , 6 males and 2 females) were selected for this study and their ECG and EMG signals were measured for 5 min each. Volunteers signed informed consent prior to the experiment. The Commission for the Ethics of Clinical Research (University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia) gave consent for the implementation of the research (Number: 01-39/239/1, date: October 5th, 2022). Time period of 5 min was chosen as it was estimated that typical ECG and EMG measurements are even shorter than that, therefore, time stability of the proposed electrodes observed in this paper should be valid for most of further tests. Volunteers were sitting during the complete duration of the measurements. The skin of volunteers was not treated before the measurements. The potato peel-based electrodes were attached to the subjects using adhesive medical tape, as shown later in Fig. 15. Moreover, during the ECG measurements, successive tasks of first contraction followed by relaxation were done, in a defined time period. The subjects were asked to contract their fist for 10 s after which a 10 s period of relaxation followed. This was done in 5 min.

2.3. Feature extraction and parameters of interest

From the collected data, heart rate (BPM – beats per minute) and inter-beat-interval (IBI) were extracted, as the primary features of interest. Additionally, NN, or normal-to-normal intervals were extracted, as they represent the time intervals between heartbeats which are not abnormal or ectopic. From NN intervals, the percentage of NN intervals which are greater than 50 milliseconds (ms), denoted as pNN50 had been calculated as a significant feature, seen on Eq. (1). pNN50 is commonly used as a quantitative measure of high-frequency heart rate variability, particularly in the context of analyzing the parasympathetic (vagal) influence on heart rate. A higher pNN50 value suggests greater beat-to-beat variability and reflects a healthier autonomic nervous system functioning, specifically increased parasympathetic activity [19–21]. Aside from that RMSSD, Eq. (2), or root-mean-squared

Table 1
Parameters of interest extracted from ECG measurements.

Type of electrode	Subject	Heart rate	SDNN	RMSSD	pNN50	Inter-beat interval	Alpha1	Alpha2
Ag/AgCl	1.	98.33	74.04	46.62	0.15	610.18	0.24	0.51
Potato peel		92.88	82.82	46.66	0.22	645.97	0.34	0.34
Ag/AgCl	2.	85.02	24.95	14.66	0.00	705.72	0.16	0.32
Potato peel		79.65	35.94	17.95	0.01	753.3	1.26	0.29
Ag/AgCl	3.	74.2	53.46	55.89	0.42	808.62	0.13	0.02
Potato peel		72.51	62.57	69.29	0.47	827.5	0.16	0.12
Ag/AgCl	4.	88.86	43.68	21.06	0.03	675.23	0.23	0.24
Potato peel		88.99	44.13	20.31	0.02	674.22	0.02	0.06
Ag/AgCl	5.	61.82	71.44	37.46	0.11	970.56	0.73	0.86
Potato peel		61.39	45.7	34.19	0.16	977.31	0.33	0.01
Ag/AgCl	6.	89.9	36.61	19.2	0.02	667.37	0.63	0.37
Potato peel		86.03	48.09	38.97	0.04	697.39	0.17	0.38
Ag/AgCl	7.	68.05	75.3	44.53	0.25	881.68	0.70	0.86
Potato peel		67.77	39.01	32.57	0.16	885.29	0.01	1.05
Ag/AgCl	8.	68.98	48.6	32.47	0.15	869.75	0.12	0.36
Potato peel		71.92	37.85	27.95	0.03	834.22	0.51	0.18

successive differences, a feature which gives insight to the function of the parasympathetic nervous system as well, and SDNN, Eq. (3) (standard deviation of NN intervals), which describes the functionality of the autonomic nervous system as a whole, are analyzed [19]. The difference between two successive R peaks has been denoted as RR in the Eqs. (1–3), \overline{RR} is the mean value of all differences of successive R peaks and N is the number of RR intervals.

$$pNN50 = \frac{\text{Number of pairs of successive NN intervals differing by more than 50 ms}}{N} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$RMSSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (RR_{i+1} - RR_i)^2}{N-1}} \quad (2)$$

$$SDNN = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (RR_i - \overline{RR})^2}{N-1}} \quad (3)$$

Detrended fluctuation analysis (DFA) was performed to analyze the effect of noise, as well as short-term and long-term correlation of the ECG signal, through coefficients alpha 1 and alpha 2 [22]. Alpha 1 parameter describes the effect of short-term fluctuations such as breathing, sympathetic and parasympathetic activity, as well as other immediate physiological responses. On the other hand, alpha 2 describes the long-term correlation in the ECG signal, which occurs over a large time interval even spanning to the whole ECG signal. Alpha 2 can detect subtle changes in the ECG [22]. When analyzing alpha 1 and alpha 2 as a whole, denoted as the parameter alpha, it shows the effect of the circadian rhythms on heart rate variability [23]. This in term indicates that for greater alpha 1 value, faster autonomic body actions are dominant, whilst for greater alpha 2 values, slower physiological actions are prevalent. The previously presented parameters are shown in Table 1, for each subject.

The features extracted from the time-domain analysis are EMG variance, mean amplitude of the EMG signal and Root Mean Square (RMS). EMG variance is a significant feature in defining muscle activity, as well as muscle contraction [24]. Common values for healthy individuals are in the range of a few microvolts. Mean amplitude of the EMG signal describes the amplitude level over a certain time period during a specific activity [25]. Moreover, RMS is a significant feature in EMG analysis as it quantifies the average power the contraction has,

aside from giving information to the overall amplitude of the signal, as well as the muscle activation level [26].

In the frequency-domain analysis, two features were analyzed. The dominant frequency, which describes the frequency at which the EMG signal has the highest energy. This depends on various factors such as the type of contraction for instance [27]. Aside from that, the amplitude that occurs at the dominant frequency is analyzed as well. This is the

most common amplitude in an EMG signal [27].

To analyze the adequacy of the potato peel-based electrodes for ECG acquisition, Bland-Altman plot was used to represent the differences between signals acquired by potato peel-based electrodes and Ag/AgCl electrodes. The plot consisted of mean values and difference values of BPM acquired with the use of the previously mentioned electrodes. Furthermore, to analyze the effect of noise on both ECG and EMG signals, as well as the goodness of the acquisition of the signals with the two types of electrodes, spectral decomposition was done, using the Fast Fourier Transform.

2.4. Electrical impedance spectroscopy-based assessment of potato peel electrodes

Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)-based assessment of manufactured potato peel electrodes was performed to determine changes in electrical properties over time. PalmSense4 impedance analyzer (PalmSens BV, 3995 GA Houten, The Netherlands) was connected to the laptop via Bluetooth. EIS measurements with PalmSense4 are performed in two-electrode configuration in frequency range 100 kHz – 1 MHz in 5 logarithmically spaced points ($f_{\min} = 100$ kHz, 177.827 kHz, 316.227 kHz, 562.341 kHz and $f_{\max} = 1000$ kHz). 3D-printed plastic holder was created with two copper stripes attached to it. In such a way it was possible to place a piece of potato peel (approximately 2 cm × 1 cm) on the top of the copper tapes and to measure electrical impedance by connecting the impedance analyzer. Three potato peel-based samples were characterized over a period of 4 h.

2.5. The architecture of the portable system for home-based personalized health monitoring

We also developed a hardware prototype to demonstrate suitability

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for EIS-based characterization of potato peel electrodes.

of the developed potato peel-based electrodes with the custom-made low-cost system for home-based personalized health monitoring. Electrodes are connected using the crocodile clamps to the analog front end. Analog front end includes electrical circuits for voltage extraction, amplification, and filtering. Measured voltage is collected using the analog to digital converter (ADC) of the microcontroller. The microcontroller acts as a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) transmitter while the mobile application on the smartphone acts as a receiver. Mobile application has module for establishment of communication with the microcontroller, and module for graphical presentation of acquired voltage. Defined sampling time is 10 ms which corresponds to sampling frequency of 100 Hz.

3. Results and discussion

This section firstly presents the results of EIS-based characterization of the manufactured potato peels-based electrodes. Microstructural electrode characterization (results of optical profilometry and 3D profilometry are provided in the Supplementary material) has given insight in the way in which potato peel-based electrodes conduct electricity and interact with liquids. Finally, the ECG and EMG measurement results and comparison between conventional pre-gelled Ag/AgCl electrodes, and the potato peel-based electrodes has been shown in the subsections below.

3.1. EIS-based characterization of potato peel electrodes

Experimental setup for EIS-based characterization of potato peel electrodes is shown in Fig. 2.

Initially we repeated three measurements for the same sample. The aim was to determine mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) values, and to, based on obtained values, determine if multiple measurements are needed. Obtained data is shown in Fig. 3(a). The average value of $100\% \cdot \sigma / \mu$ was about 1%, with maximum of 2.44%, which indicated that single measurements can be performed, as that will provide faster results and easier data processing.

Measured values of impedance modulus are shown in Fig. 3. All three samples demonstrated the increase of impedance modulus with time. This can be correlated with the water loss and observed dryness of all samples.

All three samples remained conductive over the observed period of 4 h, but there are some differences in order of relative impedance changes. For example, impedance of Sample 1 increased just 1.25 times at the end of the fourth hour, when compared to the initial value at the beginning

Fig. 3. (a) Mean and standard deviations of three times repeated measurements for the single electrode, (b)-(d) Impedance modulus changes of analyzed three samples of potato peel-based electrodes.

Fig. 4. Comparison of features acquired by conventional and potato peel-based electrodes: (a) Heart rate; (b) Inter-beat interval;.

Fig. 5. Comparison of features acquired by conventional and potato peel-based electrodes: (a) RMSSD; (b) SDNN; (c) pNN50.

Fig. 6. Comparison of features acquired by conventional and potato peel-based electrodes: a) Alpha 1; b) Alpha 2.

of measurement. Impedance of Sample 2 increased around 1.45 times, while the Sample 3 exhibited the highest level of increase (2.34 times). Observed changes can be explained by tolerances due to manual cutting of peel. The major conclusion of this analysis is that potato peel-electrodes showed electrical stability over the period of 4 h, which is of the primary interest in the case of ECG/EMG electrodes.

3.2. ECG measurements

ECG measurements were done using three electrode system, on the left and right arm, and on the left leg, for the DRL (Driven Right Leg)

electrode. As described above, the measurement process took 5 min. The sampling frequency of Biopac acquisition unit was set to 2 kHz, enabling the collection of data from which heart rate, inter-beat-interval, NN intervals were extracted. Moreover, from NN intervals pNN50 had been calculated. Aside from that RMSSD and SDNN are analyzed. Through DFA, coefficients alpha 1 and alpha 2 were calculated. The previously presented parameters are shown in Table 1, for each subject.

The resulting BPM, IBI and pNN50, averaged over the whole population of volunteers are shown in Fig. 4(a), (b) and (c), respectively. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the mean values of all the features compared between the potato peel-based electrode and the conventional electrode

Fig. 7. a) Results of ECG measurement with Ag/AgCl electrodes; b) Results of ECG measurement with potato peel-based electrodes.

Fig. 8. Bland-Altman plot of BPM for 8 involved subjects.

are close to each other, whilst the standard deviations vary. Most importantly when analyzing the features extracted from ECG signals measured by potato peel-based electrodes, the standard deviation of the heart rate and inter-beat interval, shown in Fig. 4(a) and (b), is lower than those of Ag/AgCl electrodes, which shows greater stability in electrophysiological signal acquisition. Fig. 4(c) shows the pNN50 or the proportion of successive RR intervals that differ by more than 50 ms. As can be seen in Fig. 4(c), the pNN50 measured by fabricated potato electrodes and the Ag/AgCl ones are comparable in mean and standard deviation.

The effect of the autonomic nervous system, is shown through RMSSD and SDNN, shown in Fig. 5(a) and (b), respectively. The acquired mean values for RMSSD and SDNN are in range of healthy individuals, with both types of electrodes. Both features show comparable mean and standard deviation values, with the SDNN feature calculated from potato peel-based electrodes has a lower standard deviation in comparison to the one attained using conventional electrodes. Healthy individuals have values of RMSSD between 20 ms and 50 ms, while SDNN is in the range of 50 ms to 150 ms [28]. Fig. 5(c) shows the pNN50 or the proportion of successive RR intervals that differ by more than 50 ms. As can be seen in Fig. 5(c), the pNN50 measured by fabricated potato electrodes and the Ag/AgCl ones are comparable in mean and standard deviation.

For short-term and long-term variability analysis, alpha 1 and alpha 2 were calculated. Fig. 6(a), shows the comparison between mean alpha 1 values calculated from ECG signals acquired by conventional and potato peel-based electrodes, while in Fig. 6(b) the comparison between mean alpha2 values, is shown. The mean values for both alpha 1 and alpha 2 are similar in value when comparing the signals obtained from both types of electrodes. On the other hand, there is a greater variability in results when analyzing the potato peel-based electrodes. On the other hand, both types of electrodes have alpha 1 and alpha 2 values below the adequate minimum of 0.05, indicating the presence of white noise. Most of the values are in the range of 0.5 and 1.5, showing positive correlation between successive RR intervals [29].

In addition to the above presented comparisons between the parameters extracted from the ECG signal collected with the potato peel-based electrodes and commercial Ag/Ag Cl electrodes, we randomly selected one short portion of the collected ECG signals when potato peel-based and commercial Ag/AgCl electrodes were applied (Fig. 7). As it can be seen from Fig. 7, the characteristic points of the ECG signal are visible.

To compare the successfulness of the process of acquisition with the use of potato peel-based electrodes, Bland-Altman plot was used (Fig. 8). The Bland-Altman plot depicts the intra-subject relations. More precisely, in this experiment, it was used to compare ECG signals obtained

Table 2
Parameters of interest extracted from EMG measurements.

Type of electrode	Subject	Mean	Variance	RMS	Dominant frequency	Magnitude at dom. Freq.
Ag/AgCl	1.	0.00057	0.01287	0.11346	81.65672	406.29792
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00535	0.07314	91.69125	244.03836
Ag/AgCl	2.	0.00053	0.00097	0.03117	149.97090	214.76564
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00128	0.03576	149.96660	485.19745
Ag/AgCl	3.	0.00058	0.00055	0.02356	150.03591	275.94132
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00108	0.03283	149.98210	162.39045
Ag/AgCl	4.	0.00058	0.00192	0.04386	30.08327	194.67476
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00102	0.03196	34.51181	135.16940
Ag/AgCl	5.	0.00057	0.00458	0.06767	149.97651	222.47785
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00492	0.07011	93.58841	218.74070
Ag/AgCl	6.	0.00058	0.00266	0.05155	149.90668	324.94198
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00353	0.05942	149.97906	244.60027
Ag/AgCl	7.	0.00058	0.00080	0.02827	150.05200	272.15280
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00095	0.03084	149.95373	576.96712
Ag/AgCl	8.	0.00058	0.00129	0.35950	149.94633	152.04916
Potato peel		0.00058	0.00259	0.05089	150.01195	175.71122

Fig. 9. Comparison of features acquired by conventional and potato peel-based electrodes: (a) EMG variance; (b) EMG mean amplitude; (c) RMS.

Fig. 10. Comparison of features acquired by conventional and potato peel-based electrodes: (a) Dominant frequency; (b) Amplitude at dominant frequency.

Fig. 11. a) EMG signal measured using Ag/AgCl electrodes; b) EMG signal measured using potato peel-based electrodes.

with the use of potato peel-based electrodes to ECG signals obtained from commercial Ag/AgCl electrodes. The mean BPM ranges between 80 bpm and 100 bpm, whilst the difference between the two signals is in the span of 20 bpm. Indicating that in some individuals the difference is up to 15 bpm, while the mean difference is approximately 4.5 bpm (Fig. 8).

3.3. EMG measurements

The acquisition of EMG signals was done by a three-electrode method, where one electrode was the ground, and the other two electrodes were put in different positions on the skin, at a location over the desired muscle. All extracted features are shown in Table 2.

The features obtained from the EMG measurements, more precisely the Variance, mean amplitude and the RMS, are shown in Fig. 9(a), (b) and (c), respectively.

Interestingly, the standard deviation of EMG variance and RMS, obtained from signals acquired using conventional commercial electrodes, is slightly higher than values calculated from EMG signals acquired from potato peel-based electrodes. The values for all the extracted features are in the expected ranges for healthy individuals. The features extracted from the frequency domain analysis are shown on Fig. 10(a) and (b), depict a closeness in the mean values. This indicates that the potato peel-based electrodes do not have a detrimental effect on the dominant frequency and the amplitude at the dominant frequency of an EMG signal.

From the collected EMG signals, one pair of randomly selected signals from one volunteer was shown on Fig. 11. Actual changes in time, from which contraction (with high and low intensity) and relaxation phases are totally visible in both cases (conventional and potato peel-based electrodes), are shown in Fig. 11.

When quantifying the quality of the acquisitioned electrophysiological signals, especially ECG, it is important to define the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), as it is an accurate representative and can be used to compare two signals. Moreover, it is not often used for comparison of EMG signals, and therefore the previously presented parameters ought to represent the value of the acquired signals. The PSNR of the ECG signals obtained with the use of the potato peel-based electrodes is 7.71 dB, which is quite low. The Ag/AgCl electrodes were used as a standard in the calculation of the mean squared error in the calculation of the PSNR. It is important to note that overall, the potato peel-based electrodes have given signal characteristics with greater stability in terms of their standard deviation. For example, the standard deviation of heart rate is lower by 2 in comparison to the heart rate calculated from signals acquisitioned with the use of standard Ag/AgCl electrodes, as shown in Fig. 4(a).

Fig. 12. Power spectral density of the three types of electrodes, showing that the power of the ECG signal is concentrated in the lower frequencies, as expected, around the heart rate frequencies shown in Table 3.

Finally, to show the effect of noise on the EMG and ECG signals, spectral decomposition was used as a comparison tool. The signals show significant overlap, even some, acquisitioned by potato-peel based electrodes, having lower noise values than those obtained with the use of the Ag/AgCl electrodes. The graphs for all subjects can be found in the supplementary material (Fig. S3 is the spectral analysis of ECG signals per individual; Fig. S4 is the spectral analysis of EMG signals per individual).

3.4. Comparison of results with *Ipomoea batatas*

In addition to *Solanum tuberosum*, we also wanted to explore the properties of *Ipomoea batatas* in ECG measurements. There are two main reasons: (1) comparison of results for the two potato types, and (2) exploring the properties and suitability of other biomaterials. On one volunteer we performed ECG measurement using electrodes manufactured from sweet potato *Ipomoea batatas*, also bought in the local store. Power spectral density of ECG signal, comparing signals recorded from three types of electrodes, is depicted in Fig. 12.

Interestingly, the ratio of Low frequency (0.03 Hz to 0.24 Hz) and High frequency (0.24 Hz to 0.49 Hz) power over all of the different types of electrodes is approximately the same, which is an indicator of

Table 3

ECG parameters on one volunteer for three types of electrodes (commercial Ag/AgCl, potato peel-based and sweet potato-peel based).

Electrode Type	Heart Rate mean	Heart Rate frequency (Hz)	SDNN	Low frequency divided by High frequency	Alpha1	Alpha2
Ag/AgCl	71.21197	1.18	0.169159	0.407024	0.063802	1.353853
Potato peel-based	69.92307	1.15	0.142125	0.407021	0.034297	1.156703
Sweet Potato peel-based	74.72815	1.23	0.102543	0.407037	0.02814	0.92994

Fig. 13. Power spectral density of ECG signal recorded using three types of electrodes.

power comparability or more clearly said, of adequate signal acquisition [30]. As the users are in state of relaxation All other, presented parameters in Table 3 are in the expected bounds.

Fig. 13 depicts the power spectral density, over the frequency range from 1 Hz to 1000 Hz, showing the attenuation of the noise signal with the increase in frequency.

EMG signals acquisitioned by using different types of electrodes give comparable results, as all of the types are able to detect the change in the EMG signal, which is the consequence of muscle contraction. This can be clearly seen by calculating the EMG envelope (orange line) from the raw EMG signal (blue line) as can be seen in Fig. 14.

3.5. Realization of the portable system for home-based personalized health monitoring

The overall architecture of the developed portable system is shown in Fig. 14(a). Used microcontroller board (Arduino Nano 33 BLE) is based on nRF52840 (Nordic Semiconductors) which belongs to the 32-bit ARM M4 Cortex family. Operating frequency of nRF52840 is 64 MHz with supply voltage of 3.3 V. It can be battery powered as well through the USB cable. Important feature is 12-bits ADC with sampling rate of 200 ksamples/s. Integrated on-board chip for BLE enables wireless access to the measurement data. Analog front end is based on the integrated circuit AD8232. The AD8232-board includes the instrumentation amplifier, operational amplifier, right leg drive amplifier and reference buffer. Mobile phone application (Fig. 15(b)) was created using the MIT App Inventor. USB connection was also used to get the data on the serial port of the laptop and to ensure comparison with values shown in the mobile application, as shown in Fig. 15(c). Volunteer (aged 35, male) with the attached the potato-peel electrodes is shown in Fig. 15(d). Electrodes were placed on the chests due to the simplicity of the created photo. The Fig. 15(e) shows 5 s of the actual ECG recording.

Fig. 14. EMG signal recorded on a volunteer using three type of electrodes (a) Ag/AgCl electrodes used; (b) Potato peel-based electrodes; (c) Sweet Potato peel-based electrodes.

4. Conclusions

The development of the green electronics, based on biocompatible and biodegradable materials, is of great importance for reduction of environmental pollution. Integration of raw natural materials, that we use in our everyday life, with electrical systems is a very important step towards lower waste production.

In this paper, we presented research on use of potato peel-based electrodes for ECG and EMG measurements. Our study showed that such electrodes can be successfully integrated with the commercial

Fig. 15. (a) The overall architecture of the developed portable system, (b) screenshot of the developed mobile phone application with the presentation of actual ECG readings, (c) volunteer with the attached potato peel-based electrodes, and (d) snapshot of the acquired data.

devices, such as Biopac Lab MP36 acquisition unit. Moreover, parameters of vital importance for health assessment, can be successfully estimated from the acquired ECG/EMG data. During tests on 8 volunteers, within the 5 minutes, peel-based electrodes showed very stable and reliable operation. The advantages of the proposed electrodes are: (1) the fact that they leave virtually no residues on the skin, (2) very economical when compared to the Ag/AgCl electrodes, and (3) biocompatible and biodegradable properties. With the integration of manufactured potato peel-based electrodes in the portable system for home-based personalized health monitoring we also contribute to easier ECG/EMG recording at home, which can be very beneficial for users who live in rural areas as the recording can be made at home and sent via Internet to the clinicians. Moreover, potato-peel electrodes do not create additional waste that has to be disposed.

Our future work is directed towards the analysis of different electrode designs, as well as long term stability and performance evaluation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Goran M. Stojanović: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Željko Popović:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Lazar Milić:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Mitar Simić:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbsr.2024.100664>.

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